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WATER QUALITY MANAGEMENT FOR UPPER CHINYIKA RIVER IN ZIMBABWE.

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ABSTRACT

Water of suitable quality supports the health of the ecosystems and that of the organisms that live in it and consequently human health. Any physical, chemical or biological condition that prevents the designated uses of a water body represents poor water quality. Effluent water is always associated with environmental and human health problems. Many wastewater treatment plants were designed to remove nutrients and pathogens. However, there are many factors that lead to their failure to perform effectively. A study was carried out at Hatcliffe Sewage Treatment Works (HSTW), a major supplier of water to upper parts of Chinyika River in Zimbabwe. The effluent pollution level was analyzed. Chemical water quality parameters were analyzed according to the standard methods for analysis of water and wastewater and biological water quality was based on results obtained by Matenga (2004). It was found that HSTW affects the quality of water in upper Chinyika River chemically and biologically. It was also inferred that upgrading the wastewater treatment plant cannot alone achieve improved water quality. However, integrating sediment dredging, enhancing public participation, institutional cooperation and internalizing of environmental externalities could improve water quality of upper Chinyika River.

KEYWORDS

Water quality management; Wastewater treatment; Natural water course; Water pollution; Effluent wastewater; Nutrients; Eutrophication.

INTRODUCTION

The chemical and biological nature of water continually evolves as it moves through the hydrologic cycle and anthropogenic activities change the natural water quality to an extent that it can not be used for its intended uses. Two kinds of waste, human and animal excreta and agricultural waste normally pollute water resources. Domestic wastewater discharges can affect the normal life of receiving water courses (Makaya et al., 2007). When the effect is more than sufficient for the natural water course to become unacceptable for its best usage then the river is said to be polluted (Ntengwe, 2005). The materials that affect water quality include acids and alkalis, organic and inorganic salts, bacteria, nutrients, suspended solids, and toxic metal and metalloids (Alloway and Ayres, 1993). These materials have direct and/or indirect impact on the natural water course such as toxicity to aquatic life, hardness, diseases, low dissolved oxygen levels, eutrophication and turbidity.

The presence of high levels of nutrients and pathogenic bacteria in public and private water systems is a priority water quality issue (Chilundo et al., 2008). Eutrophication has become a major challenge for streams and rivers receiving high levels of nutrients. This has rendered many rivers non navigable and some rivers have become dead such that the water resources derived from them are no longer accessible and or not usable (Liwenga, 2008). Many livelihoods that were being derived from these rivers are now oblivious. Thus, many communities have been deprived of valuable resources hence increased impoverishment. Furthermore, there is a health risk associated with physical contact with waters receiving sewage effluent because sewage treatment plants do not totally eradicate pathogenic bacteria (Sedlak, 1991).

The management of effluent from sewage treatment plants is currently experiencing a trend away from the traditional practice of waterway discharge (Matenga, 2004). Since direct water discharge is no longer permitted both intensive peri-urban industries and sewage treatment plants have attracted interest of community and regulating authorities because of their potential to contaminate land and water resources (ZINWA, 2000). Wastewater effluents have however become a valuable source of water and nutrients in irrigation and can be recycled for industrial purposes or used as a supplement to portable water supplies. Nutrients that are normally limiting in freshwaters are phosphorus and nitrogen and these are supplied to algae in sewage effluent in the form of phosphate and nitrate (Mlambo, 2005).

An increase in growth of algae compounded with an increase in plant growth is an indication of eutrophication. The presence of algae affects the aesthetic value of water in water supply while the value of water in recreation and aquaculture is compromised (Voutsas et al., 2001). Nitrate is highly mobile and can very easily leach to ground waters and may concentrate there, making water unsafe for drinking. The effects of nitrogen discharges from wastewater treatment facilities include ammonia toxicity to aquatic life, adverse public health effects and decreased suitability for use (Mayo and Bigambo, 2005). In domestic wastewater, nitrogen exists in the form of urea or protein, while in industrial wastewater it generally occurs in the effluent from chemical industries (Lie, 1996). Total inorganic nitrogen, is the form which is utilized by phytoplankton for growth. Another form of nitrogen, ammonia, has an offensive smell at low and high concentrations and exerts high oxygen demand on water, over four times its own weight (Winker and Thomas, 1978). Nitrates are considered acutely toxic because they can be reduced in the stomach or by saliva to nitrites hence induce methemoglobinemia in infants (Barnes and Bliss, 1983).

Concentrations above 0.1 mg P/L are considered to be sufficient to trigger algal growth in fresh water systems (ANZECC, 1992). On the other hand, condensed and organically bound phosphorus in the activated sludge will be converted to orthophosphate (Park et al., 1997). Thus, total phosphorus in the effluent will be primarily orthophosphate, although there will be some organic phosphorus contained in suspended solids. However, effluent containing Total nitrogen (TN) of 3-10 mgN/L and Total Phosphorus (TP) of 0.3-1.0 mg P/L is allowed to be discharged to sensitive river and estuarine environments (Biswas et al., 1999).

This paper describes the field based research study undertaken to analyze the pollution and describe the water quality of upper Chinyika River. It also presents options and opportunities for improving the river water quality with respect to nutrient and bacterial loading of the river.

Study Area

Zimbabwe is divided into seven catchments regions. The study area is located within the Mazowe River drainage catchment in the upper Mazowe sub-catchment, hence the need to take measures against polluting the water course, thus safeguarding the environment and public health. River water downstream is used for agricultural, portable and recreational purposes. Residents from a nearby squatter settlement use Chinyika River for both portable and non portable purposes. In this study upper Chinyika River in Hatcliffe area is studied. Hatcliffe area has a population of 23 834 according to the population census of 2002 conducted by the central statistical office of Zimbabwe. Hatcliffe area has high population density because the suburb was developed from informal settlements which are still mushrooming in the area due to availability of cheap land and low cost housing facilities.

Chinyika River receives its water from effluent water from HSTW, which is the main source of water and storm water runoff, the storm water is drained through open water channels from the Hatcliffe High density suburbs. The sewage collection is by gravity and as such, the catchment for sewage and rainfall runoff is almost the same. On average the Hatcliffe catchment area generates sewage flow of between 2.5 and 3.5 ML/day which treats predominantly domestic sewage. The full development of Hatcliffe catchment area (planning horizon up to 2010 according to Harare Combination Master Plan) will result in wastewater generation of 15 ML/day.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Data collection

Influent and effluent samples for each parameter (Total Phosphorus- TP; Total Nitrogen- TN; Chemical Oxygen Demand- COD, Alkalinity; Dissolved Oxygen- DO, and pH) were taken and analyzed. Sampling for chemical parameters was done on hourly bases for 24 hours over two sampling campaigns. These campaigns were conducted from 1200 hours on 22 April 2006 to 1200 hours on 23 April 2006 and from 1200 hours on 27 April 2006 to 1200 hours on 28 April 2006. Historic data was used to compare the influent and effluent chemical parameters with those obtained from the two sampling campaigns. Data on microbial parameters was adopted from Matenga, (2004).

Raw wastewater samples were collected at the inlet just after the grit removal chamber. Activated sludge was sampled from the return activated sludge sump while the effluent was sampled at the discharge point, that is, before the cascade. Samples collected were kept in a cooler box, preserved and analyzed using standard sample preservation and testing methods outlined in Table 1. Total phosphorus, Nitrates, Dissolved oxygen, pH and temperature were tested in the field.

Table 1. Analytical methods

Chemical parameter	Method
Chemical Oxygen Demand	Standard Method 5220
Total Phosphorus	Standard Methods 4500-P
Alkalinity	Standard Methods 2320
Nitrogen	Standard Methods 4500-N
pH	Standard Methods 4500-H+

Sample analysis

Influent and effluent chemical parameters were analyzed using the standard methods for the analysis of water and wastewater, (APHA, 1995).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Chemical Water Quality

The mean influent and effluent wastewater characteristics for Hatcliffe Sewage Works for the two sampling periods are summarized in Table 2. Zimbabwean standards (ZINWA) for safe disposal of effluent into surface waters were used to establish the level of pollution of the receiving watercourse.

Table 2. Summary influent and effluent results for the two sampling programmes

Parameter	Influent (mg/L)	Effluent (mg/L)	Zimbabwe Effluent Standards (mg/L)
Total Phosphorus	3.9 ± 1.2	0.75 ± 0.2	0.5
Nitrate Nitrogen		2.4 ± 0.2	3
Ammonium Nitrogen	33 ± 5	0.3 ± 0.1	0.5
COD	394 ± 70	49 ± 16	60
DO	0.14 ± 0.05	0.10 ± 0.08	60%
pH	7.9 ± 0.7	8.0 ± 0.6	6-9
Alkalinity	315 ± 75	221 ± 18	No set limit

Results from city of Harare on Hatcliffe Sewage Works are shown on Table 3 for the period January 2000 to March 2006.

Table 3. Summary influent and effluent results for January 2000 to March 2006 (adapted from City of Harare on HSTW)

Parameter	Influent (mg/L)	Effluent (mg/L)	Zimbabwe Effluent Standards /(mg/L)
Total Phosphorus	17 ± 8 (n=40)	2.5 ± 1.5 (n=41)	0.5
Nitrate Nitrogen		1.4 ± 1.1(n=36)	3
Ammonium Nitrogen	73 ± 26(n=42)	0.5 ± 0.1 (n=42)	0.5
COD	1286 ± 737(n=41)	40 ±22(n=40)	60
Total Alkalinity	367 ± 97(n=42)	157± 40(n=42)	No set limit
pH	8.0 ± 0.6(n=41)	8.0 ± 0.4(n=40)	6-9

Table 3, shows the changes in the water quality in terms of the major pollution indicators, Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), Total Nitrogen (TN), and Total Phosphorus (TP), DO, pH, and Alkalinity.

Total Phosphorus

The effluent total phosphorus concentration for the first sampling period was 0.8 ± 0.2 mg TP/L and 0.7 ± 0.2 mgTP/L for the second sampling period. An average effluent concentration of 0.75 mg TP/L was outside the standard limit (ZINWA) of 0.5 mg TP/L. This result could be attributed to the presence of nitrogen in the anaerobic zone which negatively affects the release and the overall removal of phosphorus. Historic data however indicate an average of 2.5 ± 1.5 mg/L which is far above the standard limit. Thus, HSTW pollutes upper Chinyika River, thereby influencing its water quality with regards to phosphorus enrichment.

Chemical Oxygen Demand

The average Chemical Oxygen Demand was 49 ± 15 mg/L and 49 ± 16 mg/L respectively for the two sampling periods. Historic data from City of Harare shows COD of 40 ± 22 mg/L. The effluent COD concentration met the National Water Authority (ZINWA) effluent COD concentration standard for safe disposal of wastewater into natural water course. However the deviation shows that there are incidences when COD exceeded the ZINWA standard of 60 mg COD/L. High COD levels are a characteristic of incumbent industrial activities taking place within the Hatcliffe community. However, domestic effluent can have relatively high COD levels.

Nitrate Nitrogen

The mean effluent nitrate value was found to be 2.6 ± 0.4 mg/L on 22-23 April 2006 and 2.2 ± 0.2 mg/L on 27-28 April 2006. The minimum effluent value was found to be 1.8 mg/L and the maximum effluent nitrate was 3.3 mg/L. This shows a 15% deviation about the mean in effluent nitrate. The nitrate effluent discharge standard of 3 mg/L was satisfied by effluent nitrate of both sampling days. Thus, the effluent nitrate load was safe for discharge into the natural watercourse. Low effluent nitrates could be attributed to a highly efficient denitrification process in which more nitrates are converted to molecular nitrogen.

Alkalinity

There is no prescribed limit for effluent Total Alkalinity but values in excess of 500 mg/L CaCO_3 in the effluent are considered toxic to aquatic life (Makinia et al., 2002). The mean effluent Total Alkalinity was found to be 221 ± 18 mg/L. Historic data shows an average

Alkalinity of 157 ± 40 mg/L. These results indicate that the alkalinity was fluctuating significantly. The nitrification process releases hydrogen ions that destroy alkalinity in the order of 7 mg alkalinity (as CaCO_3) for every gram of ammonium nitrogen nitrified.

Dissolved Oxygen

The average dissolved oxygen concentration was found to be 0.13 ± 0.07 mgO/L and 0.10 ± 0.04 mgO/L during the first and second sampling periods respectively. The effluent DO concentrations are an indication of oxygen utilization and or aeration potential of the biological nutrient removal system. Dissolved oxygen concentrations have no direct impact on human health (WHO, 1996).

pH

The effluent pH was found to be 8.0 ± 0.6 for the two sampling periods. The result suggests that the wastewater alkalinity was adequate to offset any pH drops. However the pH is outside the optimal range for denitrification despite being within WHO and ZINWA limits for effluent disposal into natural water courses.

Upgrading the wastewater treatment plant has been very slow mainly due to insufficient investment in the domestic wastewater treatment sector, which has been mainly financed by the local government. It has become more difficult for the governmental budget to afford the financial support so that many wastewater treatment facilities designed in the plan have not been constructed. Even if they were constructed they usually can not be operated as effectively as designed (Nhapi, 2004).

Microbial Water Quality

Matenga (2004) gives microbial (indicator organisms) removal efficiency of HSTW on different dates within the same indicator group and among the indicators.

The wastewater treatment efficiency of the Hatcliffe Sewage Treatment Works on different dates with regards to Streptococci (FS), E.Coli (FC) and Total coliforms (TC) is shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Bacteriological water quality results (adapted from Matenga, 2004)

Sampling Period	Sampling Campaigns	FS %	FC %	TC %
04/02/2004- 22/04/2004	7	94.2 ± 0.9	99.2 ± 0.4	98.9 ± 0.9

Results (Table 4) indicate that the plant is not consistent with respect to its treatment efficiency. Streptococci efficiency ranged from 70% to 99.9%, E.Coli ranged from 98.87% to 99.4% while total coliforms had efficiencies ranging from 97.55% to 99.95%. On some occasions, the removal efficiency was the expected outcome. However, variations of the removal efficiency for all the indicators were due to the variability of the influent sewage characteristics. The influent sewage characteristics are normally a function of sampling time. The variations observed in the study were due to hourly or daily variations in sewage loadings resulting from the established habits of the Hatcliffe community (Metcalf and Eddy, 1991). Removal of indicators and pathogens varies at different facilities and also at different treatment stages (Scott et al., 2003).

Treatment efficiency is also influenced by storm run-off. Storm water has a tendency of reducing the treatment efficiency due to increased wastewater flow especially in gravity systems. For Hatcliffe Sewage Treatment Works, the breakdown of the fermentation basin stirrer and non working anoxic basin 1 had no direct effect on the treatment performance of the plant with regards to indicator bacteria. However, the observed fluctuations in treatment efficiencies could be attributed to breakdowns and varied wastewater loading. These treatment inefficiencies have a bearing on the receiving watercourses.

Sewage effluent was perceived as the source of pathogens and as such *Shigella* was found not to be a result of faecal contamination, while *Salmonella* presence was found to be correlated to the indicator bacteria (Matenga, 2004). There is a possibility of having *Shigella* spp. freely living in the environment (Grunnet and Nielson, 1969) and (Lee et al., 1982) found out that *Salmonella* spp. and *Vibrio* spp. have niches in the environment. In the final effluent it was shown that the activated treatment process did not remove all the pathogens. This is because an efficiency of 99.9% *Salmonella* reduction is what is attainable in a properly working activated sludge system (Yaziz and Lloyd, 1979).

Although bathing is prohibited at the site of the sewage effluent disposal, the informal settlement uses the effluent water for bathing and laundry, and there is a possibility of children and infants drinking the water during bathing and swimming thereby posing a health hazard. Biological monitoring of rivers receiving sewage effluent should be done systematically and consistently and legislation that control the reuse of effluent from wastewater treatment works should be put in place and enforced (Hammer and Hammer, 1996).

Thus, it is evident that HSTW has a direct effect on water quality of Upper Chinyika River as shown by the chemical and biological quality of the effluent. HSTW could be upgraded and be more efficiently operated to achieve better results. It has been recognized that market oriented systems and mechanisms should be embodied into the water and wastewater systems. However, considering the inertia of the traditional mechanisms of the planned economy, it will take long time for Zimbabwe to reform the wastewater treatment sector into a market oriented and cost effective system. And as such other options should be incorporated into the wastewater management in order to better manage water quality of receiving waters.

Complementary Measures

Water quality issues and environmental degradation on upper Chinyika River could be abated and enhanced through institutional cooperation, public participation and internalization of environmental externalities (Wang et al., 2006). These are the most critical considerations for not only the basin but also for the whole of Zimbabwe to achieve a sustainable society.

The following are some of the mitigatory measures that can be adopted to compliment resuscitation of upper Chinyika River.

Sediment dredging

Sediment dredging is proposed to achieve improved water quality; however, long term effectiveness and potential impacts on the ecosystems remain uncertain and require further investigation (Mathuthu, 1993). Secondary pollution from dredged sediments may occur.

The sediments may contain many toxic and hazardous substances and if not appropriately handled may bring pollution to areas such as soils, surfaces and groundwater (Moyo, 1997).

Institutional Cooperation

All administrative institutions should be actively involved in protecting human health, water resources and the environment. In Zimbabwe these include the Ministry of Health and Child Welfare, Ministry of Water Resources Development, Ministry of Environmental and Tourism, Zimbabwe National Water Authority ZINWA, Environmental Management Agency, EMA and Catchment councils. To promote cooperation among different entities, it is urgently necessary to establish a basin authority that is capacitated and is powerful enough to be responsible for the overall planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of health, water and environmental protection programmes (Wang et al., 2006).

Public participation

Sustainable environmental protection requires the involvement of all stakeholders through the policy making and implementation processes (Bewket and Sterk, 2002). Such participation is associated with increased mobilization, higher efficiency, better understanding and social cohesion, more cost effective services, greater transparency and accountability and strengthened capacity of the public to learn and act.

Internalization of environmental externalities

The classical environmental economic theory attributes environmental problems to the failure to internalize externalities (Wang et al., 2006). The costs of externalities are borne by the society as a whole and are not reflected into prices of market transaction. Thus to overcome this, the concept of green GDP which includes externalities in economic accounting system should be introduced. However, in as much as cost recovery is concerned, service delivery system is likely to collapse as a result of non payment of the services received. People especially low income earners may resort to other alternatives which may be even more detrimental to human and ecological integrity.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A field based study was done to identify and quantify the pollution, identifying the sources and draw up a plan of action to improve the water quality of upper Chinyika River. The methodology comprised of field observation, a detailed water quality analysis and recommending mitigation measures. Chinyika River water quality can not be improved by enhancing the treatment processes alone but also by factoring in public participation, institutional cooperation, sediment dredging and by internalizing environmental externalities. Thus, an integrated approach is inevitable if sustainable water quality management is to be achieved for upper Chinyika River.

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